

Identifying Suspicious Ecological Interactions in the Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI) Database

Information Visualization Study

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Abstract—The age of digitization has led to a deluge in openly accessible digital biodiversity data, which includes datasets that consist of interactions between species (e.g., predator-prey). Our proposed visualization approach tackles the problem of identifying suspicious interactions for researchers such that possible data errors or unexpected claims can be detected in a quick manner. By using a heat map at different taxonomic levels to indicate commonality of interactions between two taxons, users of GloBI can easily visualize the trustworthiness of a record. The resulting visualization shows that this approach is a viable option to aid in the identification of suspicious ecological interactions. Looking forward, the results of this study could be used as a tool to help GloBI users understand the shortcomings of a dataset, and to be able to identify cross-referenced and non-cross-referenced records more systematically.

Index Terms—Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI), biodiversity informatics, species interactions, quality management, ecological interactions, visualization

INTRODUCTION

The Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI) dataset and tools provide scientists with aggregated species interaction data. Although GloBI is an innovative way to create datasets for testing of ecological hypotheses (Poisot et al., 2016), current evaluations of GloBI and other ecological datasets find the main downfall is that the aggregating of data creates a crowd-sourced review process (Poelen, Simons, & Mungall, 2014) (Hortal, J. et. al. 2015).

The goal of this project was to develop a visualization that would inform users of the shortcomings of GloBI and inform both end-users and GloBI developers to try to improve them. The visualization was envisioned as intuitive and simple, allowing end-users to easily judge suspicious ecological interactions as well as cross-referenced records at a glance. In narrowing down what parts of the data would be best to use, we decided to define a term that could be used to describe the sources of each record. The term “cross-referenced record” would be crucial in refining our dataset to eliminate possible untrustworthy or otherwise outlying data. Our intended outcome with this was to improve and expand the way GloBI provides data, enabling users to identify possible issues in the data, caused by software bugs, data errors, or conflicting professional opinions.

Defining Suspicious Interactions

For the purposes of this project, the term suspicious interaction was defined in two different ways. One being: interactions between species that happen infrequently and are, thus, unlikely (i.e., a polar bear interacting with an orangutan). In other words, rare interactions would be suspicious. The other being: directions of interactions that happen infrequently and are unlikely (i.e., a seal eating a whale).

Data Description

The first thing we did in our approach was to acquire the dataset from GloBI. GloBI provides various formats of their datasets, each providing a different purpose based on user needs: interactions.tsv.gz, interactions.csv.gz, and interactions.nq.gz (1) provide species interactions tabulated as pairwise interactions in a comma or tab separated format, as well as the resource definition framework format; taxonMap.tsv.gz and taxonCache.tsv.gz use the hierarchies of the species to create a map, which uses identifiers mapped to each name; the Darwin Core Archives (7) are aggregated as a custom, occurrence level, association extension; and the neo4jv1.9.9 (6) graph database contains a neo4j database snapshot containing a graph representation of the species interaction data. We decided to use interactions.tsv.gz, which was most useful for a heatmap approach.

The dataset consists of a total of 3,473,723 records in the data set, which is a tab separated file obtained from the GloBI website’s data repository(1). There are 80 different features for each row and 37 different types of interactions (eats, kills, PreysOn, etc.)

Figure 1. A basic model of a single record in the GloBI dataset

Out of the 80 features/dimensions, 37% or 30/80 features/dimensions contain less than 50% of data, and after cleaning the dataset of duplicate values, the 37% goes up to 40%. This number was calculated by finding out the percentage of null values per feature/dimension. It should be noted that these null values are a result of the way the aggregate data was collected and aggregated, and how information was not collected in some studies since it was not relevant to their research. Figure 2 is a visual representation of the null values of the dataset.

Figure 2. Distribution of null values for each attribute in the GLoBI dataset

METHODS

We began by downloading the static interaction data, interactions.tsv.gz, from the GLoBI project's data repository(1). The data was processed using Python to generate a subset where each record contained the source and target taxon names at each taxonomic rank, the interaction type, and the reporting source name space.¹ We created a unique-interactions data set from this subset by grouping records using the fields SourceTaxonName, InteractionType, TargetTaxonName, and SourceNameSpace; then filtering to remove duplicates. This unique-interactions data set was the basis for generating all subsequent heat map visualizations.

Our visualization schema is a series of heat maps showing source interaction counts aggregated along the source and target name-rank paths. This means that for a given source and target species of interest, we created heatmaps showing interactions between their respective Kingdoms, Phyla, Classes, Orders, Families, Genera, and Species.

¹ The complete list of variables selected was: sourceTaxonName, sourceTaxonSpeciesName, sourceTaxonGenusName, sourceTaxonFamilyName, sourceTaxonOrderName, sourceTaxonClassName, sourceTaxonPhylumName, sourceTaxonKingdomName, interactionTypeName, targetTaxonName, targetTaxonSpeciesName, targetTaxonGenusName, targetTaxonFamilyName, targetTaxonOrderName, targetTaxonClassName, targetTaxonPhylumName, targetTaxonKingdomName, sourceNameSpace.

At the species to species level, the data was grouped by interaction type before generating unique sourceNameSpace counts. This allows the user to see the degree of support for different types of interactions across different datasets.

For each taxonomic rank-view above the species level (such as genus, family, etc), the data was filtered by the next higher source and target taxonomic ranks. E.g. to create the Family to Family interactions the data was filtered by the source and target Order before further processing.

We grouped the filtered data by the source and target ranks of interest, and counted the number of unique sourceNameSpaces across all types of interactions. By combining all interaction types at this stage we create an overview which allows the user to see whether there is any additional support for related taxa interacting.

We converted the sourceName, targetName, and unique source-counts into a pivot table and used that as the basis for creating our heat maps. The heat map displays directional interactions with the source species in the vertical axis, target species along the horizontal axis, and unique source counts presented in the intersecting cells. We color coded each cell to make it easy to visually distinguish the amount of confirmation for each relationship.

Defining CR (Cross Referenced) Records

For the purposes of this project, the term cross-referenced record was defined as an interaction that is cited by more than one unique source. The more sources an interaction has, the more cross-referenced the record could be considered.

RESULTS

Figure 3. Interactions at a Kingdom level

Figure 4. Interactions at a Phylum level

Figure 7. Interactions at a Family level

Figure 5. Interactions at a Class level

Figure 8. Interactions at a Genus level (left) and Species level (right)

Figure 6. Interactions at an Order level

Heatmap Description

In the Heatmap - Each box represents an interaction between a species on the x-axis and a species on the y-axis. The darkness of the shade is determined by the number of times this interaction is listed; interactions with a high level of documentation will appear darkest, and those with a lower frequency of occurrence will have the lightest shades. The benefit of this visualization is that it can work with a large set of data, and the most suspicious interactions will be easily identifiable due to their color. On a final visualization, those specific interactions will be labeled and listed. The drawback is that more subtle errors will not show, as this best shows outliers in data. These set of visualizations were generated from interactions with the source species *Pieris rapae* and the target species *Brassica oleracea*.

DISCUSSION

Challenges with data

The two major challenges that we faced with the dataset were

1. Data sparsity
2. Data skewness

As shown in Figure 2, many values are missing across records as a result of how the data is sourced. These incomplete records could still be used since our visualizations focus on more complete attributes. It is assumed there will be no higher taxonomic

visualizations for an interaction if those taxonomic classifications do not exist. The records themselves were also skewed towards specific kingdoms. Figure 10 shows the frequency of kingdoms represented in the data, with *Animalia* and *Plantae* making up and majority of the records. This is something researchers using these visualizations will need to consider. Lastly, there were a few troubling records in GloBI. We found instances of inverse relations (A plant, Swedish Whitebeam (*Sorbus intermedia*) is listed as eating several different types of beetles ex. Longhorned Beetle(*Phymatodes testaceus*). The reverse of this interaction is also published.), as well instances of the same species having different species names as a result of being input from different researchers. There aren't many of these false records, so aggregate counts in the heatmaps should not affect the decision of a suspicious interaction.

Figure 9. The distribution of kingdoms in interactions, on a regular scale (left), and a logarithmic scale (right)

Challenges with the definition of a cross-referenced record

Defining non-suspicious interactions was difficult because there is no one definition, and inherently is a very subjective issue to solve. Different researchers might define it differently, therefore it was important that we define it numerically. In this way, the expression of a cross-referenced record would not depend on this definition of a non-suspicious interaction.

The question posed was how to communicate a suspicious interaction that can aid researchers. To tackle this problem, we initially chose to create a co-occurrence network that would visually communicate suspicious interactions. We also wanted to create a heatmap that would indicate the level of suspiciousness of interactions shown in network. We soon realized that the co-occurrence network did not provide any insights when it came to identifying suspicious interactions in a research situation. This is because the lack of clear numeric values made it difficult to judge suspicion.

The heatmap visualization shows the support or likelihood of an interaction occurring. This method works better than a co-occurrence network since it gives a clear representation of how many sources an interaction has at any given level of the dataset. The

results show a clear and concise workflow of visualizing the support or likelihood of non-suspicious interactions across the entire taxonomic path - from kingdom, to phylum, to class, then order, family, genus and down to species level. The visualizations shown in the results represent the interactions between two specific species, but they can be generated on any desired interaction. This is a powerful tool that will allow researchers to check any interaction at any desired level. We hope to increase the utility of this tool by soliciting more feedback from researchers and working on providing a dynamic web-based heatmap. Using heatmaps to visualize interactions solves the challenge of numerically defining a suspicious interaction. With the presence of the heatmap at different taxonomic ranks and knowing the sources that cite that interaction, we can be fairly confident in stating that all interactions with more than one source are more likely to be not suspicious. However, not all interactions with one source are suspicious. The interaction could be rare, or just not well represented in the dataset. For this reason, we include heatmaps at every level. This methodology allows us to get around the sparsity of the dataset and get closer to gaining insight in finding suspicious interactions.

CONCLUSION

The heatmap approach was an ideal solution to solve challenges with sparsity, skew, and different definitions of suspicious interactions of the GloBI dataset. The collection of heatmaps are the tools that would allow a researcher to determine if an interaction was suspicious in their own definition. The heatmaps are specific in what they explicitly show, but vague in interpretation. In the future, an expansion of this research work can be imagined in an interactive tool, accessible directly from the GloBI website. It would allow for researchers to tinker with and find the support for certain interactions to make their research more robust, along with ancillary visualizations supporting the heatmap to further drill down into the data.

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